

BioMedData Deliverable D3.4

Determining best practices and specific solutions for data handling

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Summary

Data management practices across Research Infrastructures (RIs) play a critical role in the production of streamlined Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data. It is important to assess how Research Data Management (RDM) practices are implemented to understand the strengths and weaknesses of data management services across facilities and organisations. The Norwegian landscape of life science research infrastructures involves a large number of data producers providing services to research users. The BioMedData project, an infrastructure established in 2020, brings together the RIs within the Life Sciences in Norway and aims at improving their data management practices.

In 2021, BioMedData together with the partner RIs, initiated the assessment of the data management routines at the RIs to bridge gaps across the data life cycle. The assessment was performed through a questionnaire designed in Data Stewardship Wizard, addressed by the RIs, covering FAIR data principles as well as international requirements (Science Europe, Horizon2020) – the findings included a lack of community-recognised metadata standards within specific domains, and the need to apply and improve responsibilities for data management implementation within the RIs.

Here, we provide a follow-up assessment that allows us to assess which RDM practices have been newly implemented or have improved over the past two years across five RIs. This report provides domain-specific findings as well as a direction towards understanding the need to streamline the processes of data production, sharing, and storage in a FAIR and cost-efficient way.

Background

The BioMedData project, initiated in June 2020 and coordinated by ELIXIR Norway¹, aims to bring together and support a network of Research Infrastructures (RIs) within the Life Sciences in Norway. While the project serves as an important platform to facilitate communication between the RIs, it also works with key stakeholders to raise awareness of data management in life sciences infrastructure in Norway. The goal of the project is to help improve data management practices while ensuring an alignment of the practices to international standards.

¹ <https://elixir.no/organization/biomeddata>

BioMedData is led by a team of Data Management Coordinators (DMCs) who are data stewards at ELIXIR Norway and consists of Project Area Liaisons (PALs) who carry out their data management tasks at the RI either through direct employment or a collaboration. The majority of the RIs consist of several sites/nodes across Norway and, given the coverage, BioMedData works to obtain national convergence to the best DM practices across several Life Science domains.

The partners within BioMedData and the associated personnel are: ELIXIR-Norway (DMCs: Korbinian Bösl, Federico Bianchini, Nazeefa Fatima), NOR-OpenScreen (PAL: Alexandra Gade), the Norwegian Molecular Imaging Infrastructure (NORMOLIM; PAL: Torill Eidhammer Sjøbakk), the Norwegian Advanced Light Microscopy Imaging Network (NALMIN; PAL: Xian Hu), the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa) Genetics (PALs: Even Birkeland, Ragnhild Valen), the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) Norway (PAL: Michal Torma), the National network of Advanced Proteomics Infrastructure (NAPI; PAL: Katarina Fritz-Wallace), Norwegian Macromolecular Crystallography Consortium (NORCRYST; PAL: Espen Åberg) and the National Consortium for Sequencing and Personalised Medicine (NorSeq; PALs: Federico Bianchini, Nazeefa Fatima).

Previous Findings

Back in 2021, the BioMedData team conducted a gap analysis to assess the state of data management landscape of the RIs¹. The analysis was a set of questionnaires created in the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), to also allow for FAIR assessment of answers based on built-in metrics feature of the DSW. Given that the RIs, within BioMedData, are heterogeneous with regards to their target user audience, and levels of maturity models and collaborations, we expect inevitable differences in terms of resource capacity and sustainability not just between infrastructures but also across the nodes of a research infrastructure. The analysis, performed in 2021, revealed a lack of internationally recognised metadata standards and data deposition repositories within several of the domains. This has been a major hindrance and influences the FAIRification of data, generated at the infrastructures, reducing the possibility of implementing best practices since the only option is standardisation of generic metadata being used.

Latest Analysis and Comparison

BioMedData now presents a follow-up effort aimed at determining the implementation status across the project and a potential roadmap for further improvements in the next coming years. Accompanied by national meetings and workshops for alignment, improvements to the life sciences RDM landscape of Norway are conducted through iterative efforts. As the field of data management evolves, it is inevitable for new gaps and trends to emerge. The exchange through BioMedData aims to support addressing these gaps and ensure that new and improved data management practices are implemented efficiently at the research infrastructures across Norway. For 2023, we have used a similar approach of performing analysis via a questionnaire; it consists of five sections categorised into 1) data management, plan, and support, 2) metadata management, 3) data delivery, transfer, and deposition 4) data management training and support, and 5) RI's RDM

structure and policies. Here we present answers from five RIs that cover various life science domains including high-throughput screening, molecular imaging, microscopy, proteomics, and genome sequencing.

Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

In the first part of the questionnaire, focused on Data Management Plan (DMP) and support, RIs were asked to provide information on how their potential user audience is made aware of a DMP and its requirements. From the list of RIs that participated in the questionnaire, NOR-OpenScreen provides a walkthrough on the use of the DSW tool to create and manage a DMP whereas NALMIN and NORMOLIM guide their users through consultations and refer them to existing resources at ELIXIR and university libraries. Overall, there is currently no hard requirement at the RIs for a user to have a DMP. In the future, RIs such as NAPI and NorSeq plan to make inquiring about DMP a part of a project onboarding process and to be able to guide users in creating a DMP. As a DMP provides key information on data attributes and features, it is important to exploit its machine-actionability to streamline interoperability with other tools and platforms. Due to limited capacity and resources, there are currently no RIs implementing such an idea. Depending on how the user needs and capacity at the RIs evolve, ELIXIR Norway could be a key collaborator to improve interoperability and data management planning.

While general RDM guidelines are in place, it is equally important to have guidelines on specific data types such as regulations on how to store and process non-sensitive and sensitive data. Being familiar with what are the Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA) of data helps to process, store, and share it in a compliant manner. All the RIs, except NOR-OpenScreen, that participated in the questionnaire currently do not have resources and guidelines to help users get started. NOR-OpenScreen provides its users information, via website, about institutional policies relevant to handling sensitive data, and also point users to the RDMkit webpage on ELSA guidelines available in Norway². This could be a good baseline approach for the rest of the RIs to help their users/staff learn about ELSA of data generated at core facilities. Knowledge of existing resources helps users to know when and how to have their research projects evaluated by relevant committees. For information on how RIs and their users collect and process sensitive and non-sensitive, we refer to the previous analysis report¹.

Metadata Management

When it comes to metadata management, previous gap analysis found that multiple RIs lack a structured and streamlined digital system that allows for metadata capture by either the RI and/or the users prior to sample submission. We also noted a lack of global metadata standards for some domains such as high-throughput screening. Since these findings, NOR-OS recommends its

² https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/no_resources

users the latest metadata model for high content imaging, Minimal Information for High Content Screening in Microscopy Experiments (MIHCSME)³, that is accepted by Image Data Resource and BioImaging including Euro-BioImaging. Overall, data managers at the participating infrastructures provide guidance on a request from users however, there are no general recommendations provided. ELIXIR Norway created a resource on life sciences data management⁴ to help guide core facilities and its users across Norway. While users are required to complete an essential metadata set, core facilities of the RIs make sure to provide metadata information related to experiments. Equally as important as metadata collection is metadata validation that involves steps such as ensuring essential metadata is captured and performing quality control of samples. Currently, some RIs such as Due to a lack of time and resources, there are currently no streamlined data validation processes implemented at any RI.

Data Delivery, Transfer, and Deposition

Data transfer and deposition play a crucial role in maintaining the integrity and accessibility of life sciences research. Efficient data transfer methods enable seamless movement of data between different platforms, reducing time spent on project management and ensuring timely completion of data analysis. Data deposition, on the other hand, ensures the comprehensive and systematic storage of data for future use. This can be particularly important for allowing peer-review, replicate studies, data mining and for ensuring the data is preserved for the long term.

We evaluated the data deposition strategies of all participating RIs. NOR-OpenScreen offers to perform deposition for screening data into databases such as European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD)⁵, and also encourages the users to deposit data into global databases such as PubChem's BioAssays. NALMIN expects end-users to deposit their data with occasional support through internet-based storage servers, despite the different IT infrastructures of universities/institutes. NORMOLIM, on the other hand, promotes the public availability of generated image data and offers digital archiving solutions. While NAPI only assists with data deposition upon request, NorSeq simply delivers the data to users and currently does not assist with data deposition. ELIXIR Norway provides documentation for NorSeq users⁶ on how data is delivered from NeLS⁷.

Data Management Training and Support

There are several ways to raise awareness about why a data management plan is a best practice i.e. providing key information about data management in a first meeting when a user approaches RI for a project, setting DMP as a requirement for a project to be approved/registered, providing

³ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02367-w>

⁴ <https://elixir.no/rdm-lookup/>

⁵ <https://ecbd.eu/>

⁶ https://elixir.no/Services-bak/data_produced_NorSeq

⁷ <https://nels.bioinfo.no/>

guidance on creating a DMP through either training and referring a user to existing resources, along with relevant tools and standards on RI's website. Training and support must be a crucial part of life sciences research infrastructures for effective data management.

It is important for staff members to be trained in various aspects such as usage licences, data security, and relevant RDM skills that go beyond data collection and data analysis components of a research project. Norway's life science research infrastructures have, over the years, built different levels of training and support for both their staff and users. NOR-OpenScreen, for example, offers the option to share analysis scripts with end-users and specifies this in the user agreement. However, they do not provide specific support for user-run analyses and have not offered any training or workshops for data management related to high-throughput sequencing (HTS). Limited staff availability has been a barrier to providing training sessions, but the RI aims to offer these in the future.

NALMIN has limited capacity to provide data analysis services. However, they are actively working on establishing an image-processing core facility and have secured funding for dedicated support in this area starting in 2024. The NorMIC node of NALMIN offers an annual training workshop covering both scientific and practical aspects of data analysis for images. NORMOLIM, on the other hand, focuses on providing personnel training to its users. They train users on sample preparation and proper use of the instrument-specific to their individual analyses. NAPI refers users requesting data analysis help to reliable tools and documentation. Some NAPI nodes do offer complete data analysis services. However, there is a need to improve communication across its nodes regarding workshops and training to raise awareness among staff members. NorSeq does not offer any support directly. However, data delivery on NeLS facilitates reproducible analysis using the Norwegian instance of UseGalaxy⁸ provided by ELIXIR Norway. NorSeq had ELIXIR Norway staff provide a workshop on data management for its staff. Given the different levels of training and support and resources at each RI, some offer specific workshops and training sessions, while others rely on external resources and platforms for notifications and guidance. All RIs encourage their users and staff to attend general and specific RDM courses provided by ELIXIR Norway.

RDM Structure and Policies

Due to the distributed nature of the reporting RIs, all operate across different institutions with their respective policies. These structures and policies help ensure that data generated through research is effectively managed, stored, accessed, and shared. A well-implemented data management structure and policies contribute to maintaining data integrity, promoting data reuse, and complying with ethical and legal obligations.

According to the NOR-OpenScreen, RDM best practices are most advanced at the University of Oslo whereas the implementation of best practices is minimal at other nodes of the RI due to limited staff, time, and funding. NOR-OpenScreen does not have an official RDM policy, and the

⁸ <https://usegalaxy.no>

responsibility for data management primarily falls on the users. However, the RI provides guidance and resources (via website) to support users in their data management endeavours. Coordination of RDM support between the NOR-OpenScreen nodes is done through emails from the Oslo node to the rest while each node independently supports their users' data management needs. In the future, NOR-OpenScreen aims to harmonise standard practices across all its nodes and address challenges in achieving this goal. Additionally, NOR-OpenScreen plans to develop standard operating procedures (SOPs) for data management operations at the node level and RI level.

At the NALMIN, the best practices for RDM differ across nodes based on their host institutes, university IT infrastructure, and funding availability. However, one common aspect is ensuring the proper storage of metadata for microscopy data. Each research institute at the NALMIN has a data steward representative who attends regular meetings to share challenges and situations faced by each research infrastructure. Collaboration opportunities are actively explored, especially among nodes under the same institute or university. When it comes to RDM policies at NORMOLIM, all sites have agreed on a common Access and Data Management Policy, although there are some differences due to unequal instruments used at different sites.

Questionnaire

The following list of questions is designed to determine and address the essentials of data management:

Section A - Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

1. How does the RI guide users on DMP? Are DMPs a requirement for the users? If so, which standard is preferred, if any?
2. Does the RI use (/plan to use) information from a machine-actionable DMP for the automatisisation of standard processes (e.g. project quota, controlled access)?
3. Is there a list of relevant regulations and guidelines for RI users on Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA)?

Section B - Metadata Management

4. What metadata standard(s), including Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) and Ontologies, are used/recommended?
5. Which part of the metadata is provided by the RI? and which part is provided by the user?
6. How is metadata entry, between RI and end-user, , between RI and end-user, validated?
7. Which (open) data formats are used?

Section C - Data Delivery, Transfer and Deposition

8. How does the RI assist with data deposition in a repository? and is this coordinated with another RI?
9. How is data delivered to users (platforms/protocols)?
10. How is the integrity of the data ensured at delivery? Are the metadata validated at this stage?

Section D: Data Management Training and Support

11. What support does RI provide to the end-user for reproducible data analysis?
12. What workshops/training on RDM are provided to the RI staff?

Section E: RI's RDM Structure and Policies

13. Are there differences in RDM best practices implementation at the different nodes of the RI?
14. What RDM policy does your RI have in place?
15. How is support coordinated with other RIs?

Norwegian Research Infrastructures

NOR-OpenScreen

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RDM Services (Summary): <https://www.openscreen.uio.no/english/services/data-management/>

Section A: Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

1. **How does the RI guide users on DMP? Are DMPs a requirement for the users? If so, which standard is preferred, if any?**

As a default procedure, when users approach us for a project we ask them about their DMP. Questions about DMPs and some small aspects of our part of the data management are also part of our user agreement template that has to be filled in by the user before the project starts. We do not have a requirement that the users have a DMP, but point them to the templates available in DSW in case they are interested in making one.

We have also made a detailed walkthrough of how to create, manage, and export a DMP using DSW. This walkthrough is available on our RI's website⁹.

2. **Does the RI use (/plan to use) information from a machine-actionable DMP for the automatisisation of standard processes (e.g. project quota, controlled access)?**

Although maDMPs are available as output from DSW, we do not currently use information from these maDMPs to automate projects and we do not have plans to do so within the next year.

3. **Is there a list of relevant regulations and guidelines for RI users on ELSA?**

No, generally the RI does not consider ELSA and expects the users themselves to have projects evaluated at their respective institutions by an institutional ethical review committee. We have links to the privacy/personal data policies at the institutions that host the RI's four nodes, available on our website¹⁰.

Section B: Metadata Management

4. **What metadata standard(s), including Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) and Ontologies, are used/recommended?**

⁹ <https://www.openscreen.uio.no/english/services/data-management/DMP-exemplar.html>

¹⁰ <https://www.openscreen.uio.no/english/services/data-management/>

NOR-OS recommends specific metadata standards depending on the type of project conducted. For high content screening projects, the newly published metadata standard for high content imaging, MIHCSME, allows the user to select from multiple recommended vocabularies, using ontologies such as experimental factor ontology (EFO). For drug screening, the MICHA protocol has guidelines for annotating compounds, samples, reagents, and data analyses and uses terms mostly from the BioAssay ontology. Screening projects conducted at NOR-OS for the EU-Openscreen (EU-OS) infrastructure use a specific set of controlled vocabulary across several ontologies, including the BioAssay ontology. We have a standalone tool for looking up terms for EU-OS projects. Finally, for flow cytometry projects MIFlowCyt is the recommended standard and also used multiple ontologies some of which overlap with the other experiment-type metadata standards such as NCBI taxonomy.

5. Which part of the metadata is provided by the RI? and which part is provided by the user?

Experimental details controlled by the RI during data acquisition such as instrument details, experimental acquisition parameters, assay conditions such as plate and well information, sample types and chemical information, etc. are provided by the RI. Experimental details controlled by the user such as biosample information, investigation information, etc. are provided by the user.

6. How is metadata entry, between RI and end-user, validated?

Currently, there is no process of validation of metadata neither internally nor metadata shared between user and RI.

7. Which (open) data formats are used?

CSV, XML, TIFF (for imaging), FCS (for flow cytometry)

Section C: Data Delivery, Transfer and Deposition

8. How does the RI assist with data deposition in a repository? and is this coordinated with another RI?

For projects within EU-Openscreen, the RI nodes executing the individual projects are responsible for deposition of screening data into the European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD)¹¹. Although this database is publicly available, it only contains data from projects executed within EU-Openscreen. We are available to assist users with deposition of screening data to PubChem BioAssays and encourage users to do so.

9. How is data delivered to users (platforms/protocols)?

Data is delivered using email clients and/or file sharing software provided by the institutions of the respective nodes. Users are prompted to select their preferred transmission method at the start of a project and it is possible to transmit encrypted data using PGP key/pair.

¹¹ <https://ecbd.eu/>

10. How is the integrity of the data ensured at delivery? Are the metadata validated at this stage?

We offer users the choice of various data delivery methods during project establishment, and there is a data transfer section in the user agreements. However, we do not have any methods for checking the data integrity at delivery, but could implement checksums as a solution for validating integrity after transfer.

Section D: Data Management Training and Support

11. What support does the RI provide to end-users for reproducible data analysis?

We have as an option to share all analysis scripts alongside data to the end user, and this is also specified in the user agreement during project establishment. Otherwise, many users take responsibility for their own analysis of data so the RI does not provide specific support for user-run analyses.

12. What workshops/training on RDM are provided to the RI staff?

No training/workshops for RDM specifically for high-throughput sequencing have been offered to RI staff. It is a goal of the project to have training sessions for RI staff in usage licences and data security, though this has not yet occurred due to limited staff availability. All nodes of the RI are notified of relevant RDM workshops and training courses shared via BioMedData, ELIXIR Norway, and RDA Norway.

Section E: RI's RDM Structure and Policies

13. Are there differences in RDM best practices implementation at the different nodes of the RI?

Implementation of RDM best practices is the most advanced at UiO. The implementation at the other nodes is minimal, but we have as a goal to harmonise the standard practices across the RI. However, this requires staff, time, and funding, which are currently limited at the RI.

14. What RDM policy does your RI have in place?

The RI has not adopted an official RDM policy. Generally, the responsibility for data management falls to the users. However, the RI provides guidance and resources for users. These are published on our website¹².

For data management within the RI, we have as a goal to prepare SOPs for node-level and RI-level data management operations, but this has not been achieved.

15. How is support coordinated with other RIs?

Support is currently coordinated by emails from UiO to the other nodes. Rarely, do the other nodes reach out to UiO with data management issues. Otherwise, each individual node supports their users' data management needs independently.

¹² <https://www.openscreen.uio.no/english/services/data-management/>

NALMIN: Norwegian Advanced Light Microscopy Imaging Network

RI PAL: Xian Hu (Edna)

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RDM Services (Summary): Data Storage and Consultation

Section A: Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

- 1. How does the RI guide users on DMP? Are DMPs a requirement for the users? If so, which standard is preferred, if any?** Our Research Infrastructure (RI) primarily guides users on Data Management Plans (DMPs) through consultations conducted during equipment training sessions. Additionally, we establish connections between users and established professional DMP services that are publicly funded, such as ELIXIR Norway. Furthermore, we facilitate the dissemination of regional and online DMP educational courses to our users.
- 2. Does the RI use (/plan to use) information from a machine-actionable DMP for the automatisisation of standard processes (e.g. project quota, controlled access)?**
We are currently in the process of constructing a data storage server, on which an OMERO server will be installed. The OMERO server necessitates the inclusion of appropriately formatted, machine-readable metadata for optical microscopy images before the commencement of data upload.
- 3. Is there a list of relevant regulations and guidelines for RI users on ELSA?** No.

Section B: Metadata Management

- 4. What metadata standard(s), including Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) and Ontologies, are used/recommended?** We recommend our user to follow the 4DN-BINA-OME metadata standard if their application does not involve electron microscopy and REMBI metadata standard if they are doing correlation microscopy.
- 5. Which part of the metadata is provided by the RI? and which part is provided by the user?** We provide instrument-related metadata, and most of it is stored in a proprietary format unique to each microscope. Users provide experiment-related metadata, including information about sample types and sample preparation.
- 6. How is metadata entry, between RI and end-user, validated?** End-users are responsible for data validation, and the RI usually provides assistance when requested by the users. Occasionally, a specific microscope's proprietary format may not capture some essential metadata accurately. For instance, the new Olympus SORA does not accurately record frame rates. In such cases, the RI will advise users to manually keep track of these missing metadata.

7. **Which (open) data formats are used?** OME-TIFF is the most commonly used open data format. In addition to that, proprietary formats that come with each instrument (e.g., CZI from Zeiss) are also commonly used for short- to medium-term storage

Section C: Data Delivery, Transfer and Deposition

8. **How does the RI assist with data deposition in a repository? and is this coordinated with another RI?** Each node in NALMIN has a different data deposition strategy based on the IT infrastructure of the host university or institute. Typically, end-users are responsible for their own data deposition, with RI nodes occasionally providing internet-based storage servers for short-term use by the end-users. We do not collaborate with other research institutes regarding data deposition.
9. **How is data delivered to users (platforms/protocols)?** Data transfer is typically conducted through university or institute intranetworks. For instance, at NorMIC, UiO, data is transferred via WinSCP using the instrument infrastructure established by USIT (UiO Central IT Service).
10. **How is the integrity of the data ensured at delivery? Is the metadata validated at this stage?** Some transfer protocols, like WinSCP, have built-in data integrity check protocols. Ultimately, end-users are responsible for ensuring data integrity and validating metadata.

Section D: Data Management Training and Support

11. **What support does the RI provide to end-users for reproducible data analysis?**
The research institute currently has limited capacity to provide data analysis services. The Oslo node is actively working to establish an image processing core facility and has recently secured funding for a 50% three-year engineering position dedicated to supporting image processing for the RI, starting in 2024. Additionally, the NorMIC node of the RI offers an annual training workshop that covers both the scientific and practical aspects of data analysis required for images collected on our microscopes.
12. **What workshops/training on RDM are provided to the RI staff?** NALMIN users are recommended to attend standard RDM workshops offered by the ELIXIR Norway, Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration, and university libraries. Regular image processing workshops are provided to RI staff.

Section E: RI's RDM Structure and Policies

13. **Are there differences in RDM best practices implementation at the different nodes of the RI?** Yes, the best practices for RDM vary and are tailored to the different nodes based on their host institutes, university IT infrastructure, and funding availability.

- 14. What RDM policy does your RI have in place?** At this stage, what we have in common among the different nodes in NALMIN is ensuring the proper storage of metadata for data generated by our microscopes.
- 15. How is support coordinated with other RIs?** Each Research Institute has one representative, a data steward, who attends a bi-weekly meeting organised by BioMedData in collaboration with ELIXIR Norway. During these meetings, they share the situation and challenges faced by each RI. We are actively exploring opportunities for collaboration, particularly when two nodes of the RI are under the same institute or university.

NORMOLIM

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RDM Services (Summary): <https://normolim.w.uib.no/how-to-access/>

Section A: Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

1. **How does the RI guide users on DMP? Are DMPs a requirement for the users? If so, which standard is preferred, if any?**

By the RI policy "Access and Data Management Policy for NORMOLIM", the users are given advice on DMP as part of their working contract. The users are also recommended to investigate the library guidance at each University/institution.

2. **Does the RI use (/plan to use) information from a machine-actionable DMP for the automatisisation of standard processes (e.g. project quota, controlled access)?**

The RI will advise the users to use Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), DMP online, or easyDMP.

3. **Is there a list of relevant regulations and guidelines for RI users on ELSA? No.**

Section B: Metadata Management

4. **What metadata standard(s), including Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) and Ontologies, are used/recommended?**

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Markup Language, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Controlled Vocabulary, and DICOM Controlled Terminology.

5. **Which part of the metadata is provided by the RI? and which part is provided by the user?**

The RI provides metadata regarding the instrument used at the facilities. Metadata from experimental conditions will include for example experimental procedures and variables, animal strain, genotype, age, treatment conditions, and groups. The users must complete the essential metadata for their own data set used.

6. **How is metadata entry, between RI and end-user, validated?**

By running quality control samples, and manual inspections of data created.

7. **Which (open) data formats are used?**

NMReDATA (Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Extracted Data format), DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine), Nifti ((Neuroimaging Informatics Technology

Initiative; file format for neuroimaging) JPEG, and imzML (a common data format for Mass Spectroscopy imaging)

Section C: Data Delivery, Transfer and Deposition

8. How does the RI assist with data deposition in a repository? and is this coordinated with another RI?

NORMOLIM encourages the users/data owner(s) to make the image data generated publicly available, facilitates the sharing of data through digital archiving solutions, and enables re-use of the data.

The open-source imaging informatics platform; XNAT-PIC: XNAT For Preclinical Imaging Centers, is an option to store, process, and share image-related studies with DICOM data. However, at present for small-animal imaging that does not create DICOM formatted data, a good alternative for repository for open access is missing for this kind of data.

Data deposition is coordinated locally with the institutional IT departments for each site.

9. How is data delivered to users (platforms/protocols)?

Raw data from the imaging systems PET/CT or PET/MR are usually stored locally at site servers. Other data is transferred by using 365OneDrive or the university file sender service.

10. How is the integrity of the data ensured at delivery? Are the metadata validated at this stage?

The servers, files and folders used are encrypted. Datasets are transferred using file-sharing software provided by the site Universities

Section D: Data Management Training and Support

11. What support does the RI provide to end-users for reproducible data analysis?

The users are trained by the RI staff. They are trained to prepare their samples and to use the instrument most properly for the individual analyses they are going to do.

12. What workshops/training on RDM are provided to the RI staff?

The RI staff are invited to take part in relevant workshops arranged by ELIXIR, Digital Life Norway, University Libraries, and similar organisations.

Section E: RI's RDM Structure and Policies

13. Are there differences in RDM best practices implementation at the different nodes of the RI?

All sites agreed on the Access and Data Management Policy, but with unequal instruments used at the different sites, there will be some differences as described above; section C: 8.

14. What RDM policy does your RI have in place?

NORMOLIMs Access & Data Management Policy:

<https://normolim.w.uib.no/files/2018/11/NORMOLIM-Access-and-Data-Management-Policy-1.pdf> This policy from 2019 is under revision in the coming months.

15. How is support coordinated with other RIs?

Through the network BioMedData, under the leadership of ELIXIR.

NAPI

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<https://www.napi.uio.no/>

RDM Services (Summary): Data storage and deposition in repositories

Section A: Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

- 1. How does the RI guide users on DMP? Are DMPs a requirement for the users? If so, which standard is preferred, if any?**
There is no requirement for a DMP at the moment. However, in the future, the RI will inquire about the existence of a DMP and make suggestions on where to find help.
- 2. Does the RI use (/plan to use) information from a machine-actionable DMP for the automatisisation of standard processes (e.g. project quota, controlled access)?**
No.
- 3. Is there a list of relevant regulations and guidelines for RI users on ELSA?**
No, we do not provide such guidelines. Regulations on ELSA are expected to be considered by the user before project implementation.

Section B: Metadata Management

- 4. What metadata standard(s), including Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) and Ontologies, are used/recommended?**
The RI has no recommendations on metadata standards.
- 5. Which part of the metadata is provided by the RI? and which part is provided by the user?**
Samples submitted to the RI can come at very different states of the pipeline. If the users performed sample preparation, it is expected that they provide the metadata. In any case, the RI provides acquisition methods and data analysis procedures/results. Some users only request the raw data and do data analysis themselves.
- 6. How is metadata entry, between RI and end-user, validated?**
Metadata provided by the user is entered during the sample submission process.
The RI uses (electronic) lab books to report metadata. Metadata entry is not validated.
- 7. Which (open) data formats are used?**

Across the different nodes of the RI raw data formats vary depending on the available instruments (.raw, .tdf).

Result files are provided as .xlsx, .txt, .sps

Section C: Data Delivery, Transfer and Deposition

8. How does the RI assist with data deposition in a repository? and is this coordinated with another RI?

On request, the RI helps users with the data deposition. However, this is not coordinated with other RIs.

9. How is data delivered to users (platforms/protocols)?

At the moment, data is delivered via email client or file sharing of UiB.

We are still working on the adoption of a platform such as SAFE¹³, that will enable directly delivering data to user-specific disk allocations. To facilitate data handling, this is intended to be done for all data (sensitive and non-sensitive). PROBE acts as a trial platform and once the system is set up, other NAPI nodes will be encouraged to implement equivalent systems.

10. How is the integrity of the data ensured at delivery? Are the metadata validated at this stage?

Data integrity and metadata is not validated.

Section D: Data Management Training and Support

11. What support does the RI provide to end-users for reproducible data analysis?

If users request help with data analysis, we refer them to reliable tools and documentation. Some RI nodes offer complete data analysis.

12. What workshops/training on RDM are provided to the RI staff?

We will work on communicating workshops and training across the nodes more efficiently, as it appears not many of the RI staff are aware of these.

Section E: RI's RDM Structure and Policies

13. Are there differences in RDM best practices implementation at the different nodes of the RI?

Yes. Implementation of RDM best practices at the single RI nodes differs a lot due to technical infrastructure, host institution and availability of personnel.

14. What RDM policy does your RI have in place?

¹³ <https://www.uib.no/en/foremployees/131011/safe>

Currently there is no RDM policy in place. We will work on increasing awareness about RDM (providing guidelines; reference to DMPs) among users in the next few months and will try to implement it across the RI nodes.

15. How is support coordinated with other RIs?

There is some coordination with local nodes of other RIs when it comes to the sample booking system, as this is something we have in common.

NorSeq: Norwegian Consortium for Sequencing and Personalized Medicine

RI PAL: Nazeefa Fatima, Federico Bianchini

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RDM Services (Summary): Delivery of non-human data to platforms such as Norwegian e-Infrastructure for Life Sciences (NeLS), offered and operated by ELIXIR Norway, that could facilitate streamlined data deposition to relevant domain repositories; work in progress on sharing instrument metadata. Sensitive (human) data is delivered to TSD, SAFE, and Hunt Cloud, with the possibility of GDPR-compliant sharing through federated services (e.g. FEGA Norway) .

Section A: Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

- 1. How does the RI guide users on DMP? Are DMPs a requirement for the users? If so, which standard is preferred, if any?**

Questions regarding some aspects of data management are part of the user agreement template to be filled in by users before data production. We have recently enriched the said template with a specific question asking about the existence of a project DMP, which is currently not a hard requirement from us. With this, we are also aiming at monitoring how common it is for our users to have a DMP and how the situation is evolving over time. We believe that when the majority of our users will have a DMP, we could make it a hard requirement and, possibly, exploit its machine-actionability in collaboration with ELIXIR. If users do not have a DMP in place, we strongly encourage them to get in touch with ELIXIR Norway and to browse the RDMkit knowledge-base from ELIXIR Europe.¹⁴

- 2. Does the RI use (/plan to use) information from a machine-actionable DMP for automatisisation of standard processes (e.g. project quota, controlled access)?**

Since DMPs are currently not a hard requirement, we have not implemented tooling for the automatisisation of processes based on the standard format of machine-actionable DMPs. We will, however, rely on the collaboration of ELIXIR Norway for these types of processes when they become standard, in particular for data to be delivered on NeLS.

- 3. Is there a list of relevant regulations and guidelines for RI users on ELSA?**

Generally, the RI does not consider ELSA and expects the users themselves to have projects evaluated by an ethical review committee at their local institution/organisation.

¹⁴ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

Section B: Metadata Management

4. What metadata standard(s), including Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) and Ontologies, are used/recommended?

In general, the RI does not require any metadata beyond the minimum requirements to produce data. Metadata is typically entered in our agreement form without using any type of semantic annotations.

5. Which part of the metadata is provided by the RI? and which part is provided by the user?

Most of the metadata should be supplied by the users, the only exception being instrument metadata and information related to the runs. While we do not require users to share metadata in specific formats, we are planning to support them if they decide to do so. This is part of our collaboration with ELIXIR, and we expect to see a standardised way of sharing our part of metadata with the users within 1 year from now.

6. How is metadata entry, between RI and end-user, validated?

At the current stage, there is no validation. We are planning to address this when we reach the final stages of the task described in the previous point.

7. Which (open) data formats are used?

FASTQ, FASTA, FAST5, BAM, SAM

Section C: Data Delivery, Transfer and Deposition

8. How does the RI assist with data deposition in a repository? and is this coordinated with another RI?

It is not part of the duties of the RI to assist with data deposition in a repository. The RI delivers data to the users, who have responsibility for the data and their preservation.

This said, the RI has adopted delivery methods to platforms such as NeLS that can facilitate the deposition to repositories at a later stage. A gap for facilitating the process would be the lack of metadata, and this is currently being addressed (see point 5.)

9. How is data delivered to users (platforms/protocols)?

The information on delivery procedures for both sensitive and not sensitive data is detailed by ELIXIR Norway¹⁵. On top of this, delivery on NIRD¹⁶ platform is also possible following a similar procedure as for NeLS in the link above.

10. How is the integrity of the data ensured at delivery? Are the metadata validated at this stage?

The data is validated via checksum. The metadata is not validated.

¹⁵ https://elixir.no/Services-bak/data_produced_NorSeq

¹⁶ <https://www.sigma2.no/service/nird-service-platform>

Section D: Data Management Training and Support

11. What support does the RI provide to end-users for reproducible data analysis?

The RI itself does not offer any support. However, data delivery to NeLS facilitates the running of reproducible analysis using the Norwegian instance of UseGalaxy¹⁷

12. What workshops/training on RDM are provided to the RI staff?

In the last year, the RI had staff from ELIXIR Norway to provide a workshop on data management for selected staff members. On top of this, some staff members also attend RDM courses provided by ELIXIR Norway.

Section E: RI's RDM Structure and Policies

13. Are there differences in RDM best practices implementation at the different nodes of the RI?

Yes, these are based on the type of instruments and the platforms that are readily available, in particular when dealing with sensitive data.

14. What RDM policy does your RI have in place?

The RI has not adopted an official RDM policy. Generally, the responsibility for project data management falls to the users. However, the RI makes use of platforms such as NIRD and NeLS and it is currently improving the processes for sharing instrument metadata.

15. How is support coordinated with other RIs?

The RI is collaborating closely with ELIXIR to improve RDM practices and support users on aspects related to the distribution of the data via NeLS and/or TSD¹⁸, and the recording of instrument metadata.

¹⁷ <https://usegalaxy.no/>

¹⁸ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

NORCRYST: Norwegian Macromolecular Crystallography Consortium

RI PAL: Espen Åberg

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RDM Services (Summary):

Section A: Data Management Plan (DMP) and Support

1. **How does the RI guide users on DMP? Are DMPs a requirement for the users? If so, which standard is preferred, if any?**

Currently, DMPs are not a requirement from NORCRYST. There is, however, a DMP template containing biological macromolecular crystallography best practice recommendations from NORCRYST available in DSW developed through the BioMedData project. The recommended standards are published as part of the Norwegian Life Science RDM LookUp (https://elixir.no/rdm-lookup/cheat_sheets/) set of information (cheat sheets) which is linked from the Norcryst homepage.

2. **Does the RI use (/plan to use) information from a machine-actionable DMP for the automatisisation of standard processes (e.g. project quota, controlled access)?**

We do not use information from maDMPs to automate projects.

3. **Is there a list of relevant regulations and guidelines for RI users on Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA)?**

NORCRYST users are expected to have projects evaluated by an ethical review committee at their local institution/organisation.

Section B: Metadata Management

4. **What metadata standard(s), including Controlled Vocabularies (CVs) and Ontologies, are used/recommended?**

We recommend that our users follow the Crystallographic Information Framework (CIF) as a standard file structure for the archiving and distribution of crystallographic information. This is well established and in regular use for reporting crystal structure determinations to journals.

5. **Which part of the metadata is provided by the RI? and which part is provided by the user?**

NORCRYST provides both metadata from instruments and lab conditions, information related to protein production, crystallisation screening and optimization, data collection and structure determination procedures and results. While we do not require users to share metadata in specific formats, we support them in accordance with Protein Data Bank (PDB) requirements.

6. How is metadata entry, between RI and end-user, , between RI and end-user, validated?

Metadata provided by the user is entered during the sample submission process to PDB. Currently, there is no process of validation of metadata either internally or metadata shared between user and RI.

7. Which (open) data formats are used?

We recommend Tagged Image File Format (TIFF) for diffraction patterns, macromolecular Crystallographic Information File (PDBx/mmCIF) as archiving format for macromolecule crystallographic experiments and results, and the 3D EM Extension Dictionary which describes structures and experimental data produced by 3D Electron Microscopy experiments.

Section C: Data Delivery, Transfer and Deposition

8. How does the RI assist with data deposition in a repository? and is this coordinated with another RI?

We generally deposit data for the users or provide one-to-one support on upload to the PDB. Repository depositions are currently not coordinated with other RIs.

9. How is data delivered to users (platforms/protocols)?

Data is delivered using USB drives from the synchrotrons, email clients and/or file-sharing software provided by the institutions of the respective nodes for data delivery to end users

10. How is the integrity of the data ensured at delivery? Are the metadata validated at this stage?

We ensure that the data is not corrupt and we validate the metadata manually.

Section D: Data Management Training and Support

11. What support does RI provide to the end-user for reproducible data analysis?

We work in collaboration with the individual users and if opted, share all analysis scripts alongside data to the end-user. NORCRYST does not provide specific support for user-run analyses. RI staff of individual nodes may provide training in sample preparation/protein purification and selected individual analysis instruments for other node members and advanced users.

12. What workshops/training on RDM are provided to the RI staff?

Currently, there is no coordinated internal communication of training/workshops for RDM specifically for macromolecular crystallography. The nodes are exposed to the more generic local RDM course portfolios. RI staff are generally very well acquainted with the technical details of PDBs requirements yet may benefit from a greater understanding of additional aspects of life science RDM such as licensing, interoperability and linking across disciplines. A future goal will consequently be to communicate workshops and training shared via BioMedData, ELIXIR Norway, and RDA (Research Data Alliance) Norway more actively across the nodes.

Section E: RI's RDM Structure and Policies

13. Are there differences in RDM best practices implementation at the different nodes of the RI?

Yes. Implementation of RDM best practices at the single RI nodes differs a lot due to technical infrastructure, host institution and availability of personnel.

14. What RDM policy does your RI have in place?

At present, NORCRYST has no official RDM policy in place. Our end users through their project's PIs carry the responsibility for proper RDM practice. We do however provide one-to-one user assistance and links to resources on our webpage.

15. How is support coordinated with other RIs?

RDM support is generally not coordinated with other RIs. NORCRYST has one PAL participating in the BioMedData bi-weekly meetings.